

A Comparative Uncertainty Quantification Study for Machine Learning-based Operational Prediction of a Realistic Heat Pipe-cooled Microreactor

Jaden Palmer^{1*}, Ryan Stewart², Xu Wu¹

¹Department of Nuclear Engineering, North Carolina State University, Raleigh, NC, USA;

²Computational Data Science Department, Idaho National Laboratory, Idaho Falls, ID, USA

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.20804132

ABSTRACT

Well-verified and validated reactor operations predictions are key to developing a digital twin of a nuclear reactor for safeguards and autonomous operations applications. This study uses a Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM) recurrent neural network (RNN) architecture to predict the operations of a Realistic Heat Pipe-cooled Microreactor (rHPMR) model. Multiple feature sets were investigated, including control element data and various flux sensor measurements, with artificial data impurities integrated into the flux sensor data. The results for the LSTM network trained on each feature set were evaluated with metrics including R^2 , mean absolute error, mean absolute percent error, and max error. The LSTM model, trained using data from control elements and three flux sensors, was found to be superior in all metric evaluations. Uncertainty quantification (UQ) of the LSTM's predictions was also performed using Monte Carlo dropout (MCD) and deep ensemble (DE) using the Gaussian and β -negative log likelihood (β -NLL) loss functions. The performance of each method was benchmarked against a known 2% relative aleatoric uncertainty present in the reactor power data. Overall, each technique was found to underestimate the aleatoric uncertainty; however, implementing β -NLL in both MCD and DE led to much more accurate estimates.

Keywords: Reactor Operations, Long Short-Term Memory, Uncertainty Quantification

1. INTRODUCTION

Modern nuclear reactors are physically complex and dynamically changing systems that constantly operate under strict safety and security requirements. Recent advancements in modeling and simulation have increased the feasibility and motivation of implementing digital twin (DT) frameworks of reactor systems. In light of the multitude of definitions for a DT across various industries, the Digital Twin Consortium provides a comprehensive and widely accepted definition: "A digital twin is an integrated data-driven virtual representation of real-world entities and processes, with synchronized interaction at a specified frequency and fidelity" [1]. DTs are widely applicable to many aspects of nuclear engineering, such as remote monitoring, autonomous operations, and reactor optimization, etc.

Achieving accurate predictions of dynamic reactor power during operations is an important aspect in generating a DT for a nuclear reactor, enabling forecasting of the reactor's future state and anomaly detection. DT frameworks are particularly useful in modeling diversion and misuse pathways [2]. By connecting this framework to a physical testbed (i.e., a nuclear reactor), real-time predictions can be made about the state of the physical system, as demonstrated by the DT of Idaho State University's AGN-201 reactor [3]. The advantages of both physics-based and data-driven approaches can also be homogenized to create a single DT prediction through the use of a physics-informed neural network [4]. In all of these studies, monitoring and predicting reactor operations using physics and machine learning (ML) frameworks are key objectives.

*jspalme2@ncsu.edu

Predictions for reactor power made by the DT that are known to be verified and validated may serve as the ground-truth when monitoring a nuclear reactor. Additionally, forecasting the future state of a reactor is of great importance for autonomous operations of a nuclear reactor. DT- and ML-driven frameworks, such as autonomous operations, remote monitoring, and predictive maintenance, are key assets in ensuring microreactor technologies are economical by reducing operations and maintenance costs [5]. Prognosis of the future state of the reactor is an imperative aspect in generating a trustworthy autonomous operations framework. Given the current state of the reactor, time-series forecasting through an ML model can provide a controller with information of the future state of the reactor, allowing for the best control strategy to be developed.

Uncertainty quantification (UQ) serves as a cornerstone in the verification and validation of models and simulations of nuclear systems. Regarding ML models, multiple methods can be applied to accurately quantify model uncertainty and to separate epistemic and aleatoric uncertainty. Here, epistemic uncertainty is due to a lack of knowledge by the model and can be reduced. Aleatoric uncertainty is irreducible because it is due to inherent noise or randomness within the data.

This study aims to compare uncertainty estimates from two methods for UQ of neural networks-based ML models: Monte Carlo dropout (MCD) [6] and deep ensemble (DE) [7] UQ. These methods are conducted using the Gaussian negative log-likelihood (NLL) loss function and a variant of the function, β negative log-likelihood (β -NLL). These approaches are model-agnostic and can be applied to any neural network model. Both DE and MCD are found to be the most popular, and have been applied to various nuclear applications [8, 9, 10]. Each of these UQ methods was used to quantify the epistemic and aleatoric uncertainties of predictions made by a long short-term memory (LSTM) recurrent neural network (RNN) used to predict reactor operations of a realistic heat pipe-cooled microreactor (rHPMR) model. Data generated by the rHPMR is given a known aleatoric uncertainty, which is used as a benchmark to understand considerations that should be made when implementing each UQ method.

To the best of the authors' knowledge, the key contributions of this study to reactor operations research are as follows:

- A comprehensive study of UQ of ML forecasting of reactor operations for a Realistic Heat Pipe-Cooled Microreactor.
- Disentanglement of epistemic and aleatoric uncertainties, where aleatoric uncertainty is benchmarked with a known noise/error added by the user.
- The use of β -NLL as a variation of the conventional Gaussian NLL loss function for better UQ estimates using DE and MCD.

The remainder of this paper is structured as follows. Section 2 provides background information of the microreactor model used in this study. Section 3 discusses the Deep Learning (DL) and UQ approaches used when predicting operations of the microreactor model. Section 4 provides the results of the DL model's predictions and compares the UQ results. Finally, Section 5 concludes the paper.

2. REALISTIC HEAT PIPE-COOLED MICROREACTOR

The rHPMR is a 5 megawatts-thermal (MW_{th}) heat-pipe-cooled microreactor model, which is generic in nature and can be used for exploring microreactor operations. The rHPMR layout and major components are shown in Figure 1. The rHPMR is fueled by 19.8 wt% U-235/U enriched UO_2 TRISO particles that are distributed in graphite. This fuel is present in the 18 hexagonal fuel assemblies that each consist of 72 fuel compacts and 19 heat pipes used for passive cooling of the reactor. These fuel assemblies are all contained within a hexagonal graphite monolith used as the neutron moderator for the rHPMR. More information regarding the rHPMR and use cases of the model may be found in [11].

Of particular importance among the feature variables used in this work are the periphery flux detectors and the control drums (CDs). Both of these elements are found in the beryllium reflector, outside of the graphite monolith. Reactivity of the reactor is controlled through 12 CDs, each of which contains

Figure 1. Illustration of the rHPMR layout and major components

a 1-cm-thick 120° boron carbide strip acting as a neutron poison. Maximum reactivity is achieved in the reactor when the 120° poison strip is fully facing away from the core, and minimum reactivity is achieved by the strip fully facing inward. The flux detectors found at the edge of the reflector region act as ex-core detectors to measure neutron responses (6 neutron and 6 photon detectors). While not truly outside the core, this approximation allows for a reasonable detector response without adding complexity to the model. In this case study, the angle of the poison strip in each CD is taken to move in unison, meaning a uniform distribution of reactivity in the reactor core. Given this simplification, to avoid overfitting the LSTM on information from flux measurements over CD angle, various subsets of the periphery flux detectors were used.

3. METHODOLOGY

The research approach presented in this study is divided into two parts: (1) training the LSTM on data containing sensor reading impurities using various flux sensor configurations, and (2) comparing UQ methodologies under a known aleatoric uncertainty. Due to the page limit, brief discussions of these two parts are presented in Sections 3.1 and 3.2, respectively. Similarly, the results are presented separately in Sections 4.1 and 4.2. The LSTM was trained using an 80%/20% train-validation split. Five operations datasets were created for testing to investigate the LSTM's ability to generalize well in predicting full operations. In both parts, the LSTM model was consistently trained on 50 epochs using the Adam optimizer with a learning rate of 3×10^{-4} and a mean squared error (MSE) loss. A batch size of 32 was used, and the sequence length in which data was partitioned for the LSTM was 30 timesteps (each 0.1 seconds long).

3.1. LSTM Architecture and Training

To predict power operations of the rHPMR, a deep LSTM neural network was used, given its strength in predicting time series data. A schematic of the architecture is shown in Figure 2. The model consists of two LSTM layers, each containing 64 units, a dense layer with 32 units, and a final dense layer with one unit to output the singular quantity-of-interest – Power. A dropout layer is placed between each weighted layer with a consistent dropout rate of 10% for regularization, given the depth of the network. Additionally, the application of dropout between weighted layers is necessary to obtain a

uniform sampling of model parameter combinations when performing UQ with MCD.

Figure 2. LSTM Model Architecture

Various data impurities were incorporated into flux sensor data to simulate what experimental results may resemble. Gaussian noise was applied to flux data using a 5.7% uncertainty standard typically found in BF_3 flux detectors [12]. Linear sensor drift was also added to each dataset to account for long-term sensor defects, where flux sensor reading drifted upward at a rate of 0.1% per minute. Sensor drift was added in this immediate and rapid fashion to capture a significant amount of drift in operations datasets while maintaining computational feasibility. Three LSTM models using different feature sets of varying flux sensors are created to predict rHPMR power. Each feature set included the CD angle along with one, three, or six flux sensors, respectively.

3.2. UQ Methods

To adequately compare each UQ method, a known aleatoric uncertainty was incorporated into the rHPMR power data for benchmarking against known physical variability. To obtain a fair estimate of aleatoric uncertainty, impurities in the flux sensor data presented in the previous section (noise and sensor drift) were removed to isolate the intrinsic measurement noise. A 2% relative uncertainty was artificially added to closely represent the physical variability that would be expected.

3.2.1. Monte Carlo Dropout

MCD is a method for quantifying DL model uncertainty through the use of dropout in both training and prediction steps. Traditionally, dropout regularization is performed during the training of the DL model and disregarded during model inference to allow each neuron to contribute to the prediction of test datasets. MCD enables each dropout layer to randomly remove neurons from the model's architecture during inference while performing T forward passes using the same test dataset. This process allows for multiple combinations of the model parameters, Θ , to be sampled from the same dataset, D , generating a predictive distribution with T samples. The predictive distribution is generally approximated to be a Gaussian function, from which a mean $\mu(X, \Theta)$ and variance $\sigma^2(X, \Theta)$ of predictions can be sampled from, given the feature and target sets X and Y : $p(Y|X, \Theta) \sim \mathcal{N}(\mu(X, \Theta), \sigma^2(X, \Theta))$.

In order to disentangle epistemic and aleatoric uncertainties, the model architecture presented in Section

3.1 includes an extra unit in the final dense layer. This allows for the predicted mean and variance to be output together and learned through the Gaussian NLL function presented in Equation (1). This dual output allows for each predicted value to be treated as a sample from a heteroscedastic (dynamic variance across input space) Gaussian distribution. Generally, applications of MCD may utilize a more conventional loss function as well, such as MSE; however, the use of MSE will only provide an estimate for epistemic uncertainty.

$$\mathcal{L}_\theta(x_i, y_i) = -\log p_\theta(y_i|x_i) = \frac{\log \sigma_\theta(x_i)}{2} + \frac{(y_i - \mu_\theta(x_i))^2}{2\sigma_\theta^2(x_i)} + \varepsilon \quad (1)$$

While this loss function allows for a heteroscedastic variance to be learned, issues regarding instability in model training and underestimation of the variance using the Gaussian NLL loss have also been found to occur. Therefore, an alternative loss function called β -NLL, shown in Equation (2), has been proposed by [13]. The $\text{stop}(\cdot)$ function prevents the function's argument from being included during backpropagation, where $\beta \in [0, 1]$. This allows the $\text{stop}(\cdot)$ function to serve as a static scaling constant. This process has been demonstrated to slow the minimization of variance during the training process, leading to more accurate uncertainty estimates. Intuitively, when $\beta = 0$, the loss function returns to the standard Gaussian NLL, and when $\beta = 1$, the loss function becomes the MSE loss.

$$\mathcal{L}_\theta^{(\beta)}(x_i, y_i) = \text{stop}(\sigma_\theta^2(x_i)^\beta) \left[\frac{\log \sigma_\theta(x_i)}{2} + \frac{(y_i - \mu_\theta(x_i))^2}{2\sigma_\theta^2(x_i)} \right] + \varepsilon \quad (2)$$

100 stochastic forward passes were performed for UQ of the predictions. A comparison of uncertainty estimates using the NLL and β -NLL loss functions was conducted, where β values of 0.25, 0.5, and 0.75 were investigated. The relative epistemic and aleatoric uncertainties obtained for each MCD procedure were compared, where the true relative aleatoric uncertainty of 2% was used as a benchmark. Aleatoric uncertainty was quantified as the mean of the predictive variance across all forward passes, $\sigma_\theta^2(x_i)$, while epistemic uncertainty was obtained from the variance of the mean prediction, $\mu_\theta(x_i)$. The disentanglement of these uncertainties is expressed in Equation (3), which is found to be structurally analogous to the bias-variance decomposition for the MSE loss function [14].

$$\text{Var}[y_i|x_i] = \underbrace{\mathbb{E}_\theta[\sigma_\theta^2(x_i)]}_{\text{aleatoric uncertainty}} + \underbrace{\text{Var}_\theta[\mu_\theta(x_i)]}_{\text{epistemic uncertainty}} \quad (3)$$

3.2.2. Deep Ensemble Networks

DE networks quantify model uncertainty by training M neural networks independently and aggregating their predictions. The mean prediction and variance are obtained in a similar fashion to MCD, where each result is averaged across M models instead of T forward passes. Independent training allows DE to provide a more robust estimate of uncertainty as the predictive distribution is constructed from an independent set of different model parameters, while MCD samples from the same set of parameters. Five LSTM networks were used to construct the ensemble, similar to [7].

The general use of DE is recommended using the Gaussian NLL loss function (or a variation) by [7] rather than simply having the ability to use MSE like MCD. This requirement arises because DE estimates uncertainty using explicit probabilistic modeling, whereas MCD uses a sampling technique. Similar to the MCD UQ performed in this study, a comparison of epistemic and aleatoric uncertainties is performed using the Gaussian NLL loss function and β -NLL loss for $\beta \in \{0.25, 0.5, 0.75\}$.

4. RESULTS

4.1. LSTM Predictions

Predictions made by the LSTM were evaluated using the R^2 score, Mean Absolute Error (MAE), Mean Absolute Percent Error (MAPE), and Max Error (ME) metrics. Global accuracy metrics can capture how well model predictions fit the data (R^2 score) and the average magnitude of errors in Watts (MAE) and as a percentage (MAPE). ME serves as a local accuracy metric, which expresses the largest residual value that occurs when comparing model predictions against test data. The accuracy and error scores for LSTM models trained using various amounts of flux sensors are shown in Table I.

Table I. Accuracy of LSTM predictions for rHPMR using various flux sensor feature sets.

Flux Sensors	R^2	MAE (W)	MAPE (%)	ME (W)
1	0.883	170.60	0.102	8,738
3	0.996	39.78	0.028	1,654
6	0.914	177.19	0.187	10,017

Overall, each model provides a good estimate of reactor power for each of the five test datasets, where the use of three flux sensors is shown to have the best performance. It may be assumed that the use of one sensor along with CD angle does not provide the LSTM with enough context to generate a precise fit of test data, while predictions made using six sensors tend to overfit to the flux data impurities. A prediction made by the LSTM using three flux sensors on a test dataset is shown in Figure 3.

Figure 3. LSTM predictions of rHPMR power using three periphery flux sensors

4.2. Comparison of UQ Approaches

The relative uncertainties from the MCD and DE methods using the Gaussian NLL and β -NLL loss are shown in Table II. Both MCD and DE are shown to produce similar uncertainty estimates, where DE generally provides lower estimates of epistemic uncertainty regardless of the loss function used. Initial estimates using the Gaussian NLL loss function are shown to underestimate aleatoric uncertainty from the known value of 2%. This underestimation is likely a consequence of the imbalance between the residual and variance penalizing term in the Gaussian NLL function as expressed in [13].

While adapting each method to use a β -NLL loss still underestimates aleatoric uncertainty, incorporating even a β of 0.25 noticeably improves the accuracy of aleatoric uncertainty estimates, particularly for DE-based UQ. Increasing the value of β is shown to have diminishing returns in estimating larger epistemic and aleatoric uncertainties. The epistemic uncertainty is found to be relatively small (less than 1% relative uncertainty for all estimates), leading to the conclusion that the LSTM has learned to create reliable predictions from the input data. For each loss function used, the model accuracy remained consistent, if not slightly superior, compared to the results presented in Table I, which used an MSE loss.

Table II. Relative uncertainty estimates from each UQ method (%)

β	Aleatoric		Epistemic	
	MCD	DE	MCD	DE
0.0 (Conventional Gaussian NLL)	0.5951	0.5807	0.1840	0.1092
0.25	0.7719	0.9463	0.5830	0.4147
0.50	0.9824	0.9672	0.7705	0.4436
0.75	1.0178	0.9900	0.7883	0.5002

5. CONCLUSIONS

This study utilized an LSTM RNN to predict the reactor operations of an rHPMR using control element and flux sensor data. The use of three flux sensors along with CD angle was found to be the most optimal feature set for providing sufficient contextual information without overfitting to data impurities. A UQ study was performed to quantify the aleatoric and epistemic uncertainties of the LSTM predictions, where a known 2% relative error was manually added to the dataset as a benchmark. Both MCD and DE were shown to provide similar uncertainty estimates. Additionally, the use of the β -NLL loss function was shown to provide more realistic uncertainty estimates compared to the traditional Gaussian NLL loss function. Overall, the results from the UQ comparison study showed that the use of the β -NLL loss function provides better calibrated results for MCD and DE compared to the conventional Gaussian NLL loss function. This UQ methodology may be evaluated on various other nuclear datasets and DL models to determine if the β -NLL loss function comprehensively yields better UQ estimates for MCD and DE.

Future work may involve the addition of another model-agnostic UQ method to generate uncertainty estimates: conformal predictions (CP). CP performs UQ by transforming a model's point estimates into intervals with coverage guarantees. These coverage guarantees ensure statistical rigor in the UQ estimates, as the methodology is mathematically supported, thereby providing a formal guarantee. A preliminary analysis has shown that application of vanilla CP is not compatible with time series data due to the data exchangeability assumption. Therefore, special treatment is necessary to apply CP for UQ using the dataset in this study.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

This work is supported by DOE, under DOE Idaho Operations Office Contract DE-AC07-05ID14517. Accordingly, the U.S. Government retains a nonexclusive, royalty-free license to publish or reproduce the published form of this contribution, or allow others to do so, for U.S. Government purposes. This research made use of Idaho National Laboratory's High Performance Computing systems located at the Collaborative Computing Center and supported by the Office of Nuclear Energy of the U.S. DOE and the Nuclear Science User Facilities under Contract No. DE-AC07-05ID14517. This work was supported in part by the National Nuclear Security Administration (NNSA) Defense Nuclear Nonproliferation Research and Development. The authors from NCSU have been supported by the Department of En-

ergy National Nuclear Security Administration through Defense Nuclear Nonproliferation's Enabling Capabilities in Technology Consortium under Award Number DE-NA0004197.

REFERENCES

- [1] D. T. Consortium. "Definition of a Digital Twin." (2024). URL <https://www.digitaltwinconsortium.org/initiatives/the-definition-of-a-digital-twin/>.
- [2] C. Ritter, R. Hays, J. Browning, R. Stewart, S. Bays, G. Reyes, M. Schanfein, A. Pluth, P. Sabharwall, R. Kunz, et al. "Digital twin to detect nuclear proliferation: A case study." *Journal of Energy Resources Technology*, **volume 144**(10), p. 102108 (2022).
- [3] R. Stewart, E. Trevino, A. Shields, K. Heaps, J. Darrington, Q. Williams, C. Pope, J. Scott, B. Baker, J. Palmer, et al. "The AGN-201 Digital Twin: A test bed for remotely monitoring nuclear reactors." *Annals of Nuclear Energy*, **volume 213**, p. 111041 (2025).
- [4] K. Prantikos, L. H. Tsoukalas, and A. Heifetz. "Physics-informed neural network solution of point kinetics equations for a nuclear reactor digital twin." *Energies*, **volume 15**(20), p. 7697 (2022).
- [5] I. N. de Candido, A. A. Rashdan, A. A. Jaoude, and J. Buongiorno. "Assessment of Techno-economic Opportunities in Automation for Nuclear Microreactors." *Nuclear Science and Engineering*, **volume 0**(0), pp. 1–20 (2024).
- [6] Y. Gal and Z. Ghahramani. "Dropout as a bayesian approximation: Representing model uncertainty in deep learning." In *international conference on machine learning*, pp. 1050–1059. PMLR (2016).
- [7] B. Lakshminarayanan, A. Pritzel, and C. Blundell. "Simple and scalable predictive uncertainty estimation using deep ensembles." *Advances in neural information processing systems*, **volume 30** (2017).
- [8] M. Yaseen and X. Wu. "Quantification of Deep Neural Network Prediction Uncertainties for VVUQ of Machine Learning Models." *Nuclear Science and Engineering*, **volume 197**(5), pp. 947–966 (2023).
- [9] A. Akins, D. Kultgen, X. Wu, and A. Heifetz. "Monte Carlo Dropout Uncertainty Quantification of Long Short-Term Memory Autoencoder Anomaly Detection in a Liquid Sodium Cold Trap." *Nuclear Technology* (2025). <https://doi.org/10.1080/00295450.2025.2518613>.
- [10] X. Wu, L. Moloko, P. Bokov, G. Delipei, J. Kaizer, and K. Ivanov. "Uncertainty Quantification for Data-Driven Machine Learning Models in Nuclear Engineering Applications: Where We Are and What Do We Need?" *Nuclear Science and Engineering* (2025). <https://doi.org/10.1080/00295639.2025.2552500>.
- [11] N. Snow, S. Shanahan, Q. Williams, I. Trivedi, E. Ryan, S. Terlizzi, C. Palmer, and R. Stewart. "Preliminary studies on diversion and misuse for TRISO-fueled heat-pipe-cooled microreactors." *Annals of Nuclear Energy*, **volume 217**, p. 111309 (2025).
- [12] R. T. Kouzes, J. H. Ely, A. T. Lintreuer, E. R. Siciliano, and M. L. Woodring. "BF₃ neutron detector tests." Technical report, Pacific Northwest National Lab.(PNNL), Richland, WA (United States) (2009).
- [13] M. Seitzer, A. Tavakoli, D. Antic, and G. Martius. "On the pitfalls of heteroscedastic uncertainty estimation with probabilistic neural networks." *arXiv preprint arXiv:220309168* (2022).
- [14] S. Geman, E. Bienenstock, and R. Doursat. "Neural networks and the bias/variance dilemma." *Neural computation*, **volume 4**(1), pp. 1–58 (1992).